

Examining the Technological Skills Among Junior High School Students Using the Path Analysis Approach

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Abstract. This study aimed to assess the impact of goal orientation and how-to videos on the technological skills of Grade 10 students in Sulop District, Davao del Sur, employing a non-experimental quantitative design with a descriptive-correlational technique through path analysis. The researcher selected 232 students using a simple random sampling method and utilized an adapted survey questionnaire, which was pilot tested for reliability and internal consistency. The findings revealed that the goal orientation among students is moderately extensive, with performance approach and avoidance orientations more prevalent than mastery and work-avoidant orientations. Technological skills were also found to be moderately extensive, with particular strength in software tools and digital communication, whereas skills in internet navigation and problem-solving were less evident. The study also found moderate usage of how-to videos, with peer recommendations being a prominent mode of engagement. Additionally, a strong goal orientation correlated with enhanced technological skills and frequent engagement with how-to videos. These relationships underscore the importance of motivational factors in shaping digital competence and the utilization of instructional videos. The study's model demonstrated excellent fit, affirming the significant interrelationships among the variables.

KEY WORDS

1. Goal orientation 2. how-to videos 3. technological skills 4. path analysis 5. quantitative research 6. educational strategies 7. Grade 10 students 8. Sulop District

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1. Introduction

In today's classrooms, technology plays a vital role in supporting learning and preparing students for future careers. However, many students still struggle to develop strong technological skills despite the growing presence of digital tools in education. Reports show that motivation, particularly goal orientation, and the use of instructional resources, such as how-to videos, greatly influence how learners acquire and apply these skills. Without proper guidance, students may struggle to maximize the benefits of available technologies in both academic and practical contexts. This situation is evident among Grade 10 students, who continue to demonstrate limited proficiency in applying and utilizing technological tools and processes, creating a pressing concern that this study aims to address. In the United States, many students struggle to acquire

strong technological skills due to various social and economic factors. Banerjee (2020) noted that inequitable access to reliable internet and digital devices is a significant barrier for learners in underprivileged areas. Ben Youssef et al. (2022) noted that the rapid pace of technological change makes it challenging for schools to keep pace with updated tools and software, resulting in outdated learning materials. Moreover, teachers may lack adequate training, which further hampers effective technology integration in classrooms. As a result, American students often exhibit varying levels of digital competence, with some significantly lagging. In Africa, the shortage of infrastructure and digital resources creates significant challenges for students seeking to develop technological skills. Langthaler and Bazafkan (2020) highlighted that many schools lack sufficient computers or a consistent electricity supply, making it difficult to effectively practice or apply digital lessons. Adu et al. (2022) also emphasize that high internet costs and limited technical support hinder both teaching and learning experiences. Consequently, some African learners graduate with limited exposure to modern technologies, which affects their competitiveness in the global job market. Addressing these issues requires improving infrastructure, reducing internet costs, and providing ongoing professional development for teachers on digital integration. Across Asia, the problem of inadequate technological skills is often linked to large class sizes and uneven distribution of resources. Yeap et al. (2021) argued that teachers handling large classes cannot provide enough individual attention to ensure that every student gains hands-on experience with digital tools. Meanwhile, Romli et al. (2022) noted that some countries in Asia focus too heavily on test results, leaving little time for creative or practical technology-based lessons. These factors hinder the cultivation of meaningful technology skills among students, especially in rural or economically challenged regions. Thus, targeted policies and better resource management are crucial to bridge the digital literacy gap in Asian schools. In the Philippines, despite being recognized as one of the most social media-savvy nations, many students still lack essential technological proficiency. Alipio (2020) noted that limited school budgets, outdated computer labs, and internet connectivity issues hinder effective digital learning. Baticulon et al. (2021) observed that teachers also require more specialized training to effectively integrate technology into their daily lessons, as relying solely on basic platforms like social media does not fully develop core technological skills. Also, unequal access to technology between urban and rural schools makes it difficult for learners from remote areas to keep pace. As a result, implementing more robust digital literacy programs in Philippine schools is necessary to equip students for future academic and career needs. In the researcher's setting, the challenge of poor technological skills among students is influenced by factors such as language diversity, resource limitations, and varying levels of teacher expertise. While some schools have invested in upgraded computer labs, consistent internet service remains an issue in certain areas. Furthermore, there is an insufficient amount of teacher training in designing and implementing technology-enhanced lessons, which often results in underutilized digital resources. Consequently, learners may not develop the technical abilities needed to thrive in today's digital world. Addressing these issues by providing more structured training programs, allocating adequate technological tools, and strengthening support systems can significantly improve students' technological competence in Davao del Sur. The review of existing literature shows several research gaps that justify the conduct of this study. From a methodological standpoint, most studies on goal orientation and technological skills rely on descriptive or correlational designs, which limit the capacity to determine

predictive relationships between variables. Few studies have utilized path analysis as a robust quantitative approach that can reveal both direct and indirect effects of instructional tools, such as how-to videos, on technological skills. In addition, earlier studies often focus on general academic performance or digital literacy, but do not specifically integrate the role of guided visual resources with motivational orientations in developing practical technological competencies among students. This methodological gap underscores the need for a study that employs a more sophisticated analytical model within a specific educational context. Meanwhile, temporal and demographic gaps strengthen the urgency of conducting the study in the Sulop District of Davao del Sur. Most available research was conducted in earlier periods when digital resources were less integrated into classroom instruction, leaving recent developments in how-to videos and technology-driven learning underexplored. Moreover, past studies have often focused on senior high school or college students in urban areas, neglecting Grade 10 learners in rural districts who face distinct challenges in accessing and applying technological skills. Addressing these gaps is timely and urgent in the researcher's setting, as local schools increasingly incorporate technology into the curriculum but lack empirical evidence on effective strategies. By focusing on Grade 10 students in Sulop District, this study not only bridges methodological and demographic gaps but also provides context-specific insights that can inform local teaching practices and improve technological skill acquisition.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

1.1.1. *Goal Orientation*—Goal orientation refers to the attitudes and motivations guiding students' approaches to learning and achievement (Alhadabi Karpinski, 2020). Moderate goal orientation enhances inquiry skills, adaptability, and critical thinking (Aarkrog Wahlgren, 2022; Sánchez-Cardona et al., 2021).

Students with balanced achievement goals demonstrate reflective thinking, self-efficacy, and persistence (Suyatna Putra, 2020). Mastery-oriented learners engage deeply and maintain resilience, while performance-oriented ones focus on recognition and comparison (Yoo et al., 2024; Mai, 2024). Adaptive goal orientations—particularly mastery-focused ones—promote self-determination, emotional investment, and consistent engagement (Rothes et al., 2022; Yi et al., 2020).

1.1.2. *Technological Skills*—Technological skills encompass competencies in digital literacy, software use, internet research, and digital communication (Owo Deebom, 2020). Students with mastery-oriented goals explore technology more deeply and develop robust skill sets (Chonsalasin Khampirat, 2022), while performance-oriented learners often focus narrowly on task completion (Yang et al., 2023). Effective use of technology fosters motivation and active learning (Abd Karim Mustapha, 2022; Chiu et al., 2019). Early exposure to books and vocational training also builds digital competence and self-employment potential (Sikora et al., 2019; Edokpolor Abusomwan, 2019).

1.1.3. *Mastery Goal Orientation*—Mastery goal orientation prioritizes competence, understanding, and self-improvement (Senko, 2019). It enhances learning readiness, academic persistence, and long-term achievement (Mose et al., 2022; Romero et al., 2024). Beyond academics, mastery goals strengthen lifelong learning and adaptability in various contexts (Hee et al., 2019; Roen Måkestad, 2019).

1.1.4. *Performance Approach Orientation*—Performance approach orientation focuses on demonstrating superiority and achieving recognition (Gómez Valdés, 2019). When guided properly, it drives motivation and measurable success in structured environments (Hoque et al., 2020; Vogt, 2022). Teacher motivation and leadership practices greatly influence

the development of such goals (Blossing Liljenberg, 2019; Kiran et al., 2019).

1.1.5. Performance Avoidance Orientation—Students with performance avoidance orientation tend to fear failure and avoid challenges (Choi et al., 2022). This behavior leads to defensive learning and reduced motivation (Usán et al., 2019; Zafarani et al., 2022). Such orientations correlate with anxiety, perfectionism, and low adaptability (Aydiner-Uygun, 2020; Stasielowicz, 2019). Encouraging mastery goals can mitigate these effects by fostering growth mindsets.

1.1.6. Work-Avoidant Orientation—Work-avoidant students prioritize minimal effort and task completion over mastery (Harnar et al., 2021). This weakens critical thinking and achievement. Addressing work avoidance requires relevant, meaningful, and autonomy-supportive learning (Stoeger Zeidner, 2019; Willoughby Evans, 2019). Classroom goal structures that emphasize mastery over performance can re-engage learners and enhance motivation (Kalali Sani et al., 2021).

1.1.7. Proficiency in Software Tools—Proficiency in software reflects students' ability to use applications effectively for academic and collaborative work (Akudo, 2022). Moderate proficiency is common, especially in basic tasks, but advanced skills remain limited (Alahi Yesmin, 2024; Kuzminska et al., 2019). Collaborative digital projects build teamwork, organization, and strategic thinking (Lavrentieva et al., 2019; Terry et al., 2019).

1.1.8. Internet Navigation and Research Skills—Students often show moderate internet research skills—competent at finding basic information but weak in critical evaluation (Zgambo Chawinga, 2019; Ay Erdem, 2020). Enhancing mindfulness and digital literacy improves research quality (Atoy et al., 2020). Poor literacy and evaluation skills limit effective online learning (Van Deursen Van Dijk, 2009; Kannianen et al., 2019).

1.1.9. Digital Communication Competence—Digital communication skills enable effective collaboration and interaction in virtual environments (Zhao et al., 2021). High competence in this area reflects strong confidence and digital exposure (Rodríguez-García et al., 2022; Iglesias-Rodríguez et al., 2021). Integration of communication tools enhances collaboration, engagement, and professional readiness (Guillén-Gámez Mayorga-Fernández, 2020).

1.1.10. Problem-Solving with Technology—Technological problem-solving combines critical thinking and technical application (Unal Cakir, 2021). Moderate proficiency indicates potential for improvement through task-based learning (Malik et al., 2019; Santos-Trigo Reyes-Martínez, 2019). Gamified and interactive environments reveal engagement but limited transfer of problem-solving skills to real-world contexts (Chen, 2019; Poonsawad et al., 2022).

1.1.11. How-to Videos as Learning Tools—How-to videos enhance understanding through visual and auditory engagement (Lok, 2019; Ugulu, 2019). Their moderate use supplements traditional learning and supports self-directed study (Powell Bodur, 2019; Faath-Becker Walker, 2020). Video-based instruction strengthens both pedagogical and technological skills across disciplines (Karanjakwut Sripicharn, 2023; Morin et al., 2019). These videos also bridge theoretical and practical knowledge, fostering confidence and continuous learning (Maziriri et al., 2020; Pratama et al., 2020; Wahyuni et al., 2021).

1.1.12. Mediating Role of How-to Videos—Goal orientation influences how students use instructional videos. Mastery-oriented learners engage deeply and revisit content for comprehension, while performance-oriented ones use videos strategically for assessments (Zhou et al., 2020; Elareshi et al., 2022; Sari et al., 2020). How-to videos enhance metacognition, motivation, and technological proficiency by

connecting goals with skill development (Liu Liu, 2020; Shoufan Mohamed, 2022; Garcia-Marquez Bauer, 2021). Integrating videos into instruction effectively mediates the relationship between goal orientation and technological skills, strengthening learning outcomes (Wang Chen, 2020; Bailey et al., 2022).

1.2. Synthesis—The relationship between goal orientation and technological skills in students reveals that how students approach their learning significantly influences their ability to acquire and apply new technologies. Literature suggests that students with a mastery orientation, who focus on learning and developing new skills for their own sake, tend to engage more deeply and persistently with technological content. Conversely, those with a performance orientation, who aim to prove competence to others, might engage with technology primarily when it aligns with achieving visible success, such as high grades or recognition. This distinction highlights the importance of understanding not just the presence of technological skills but the underlying motivations driving their acquisition and utilization. How-to videos have emerged as a potent tool in education, particularly in enhancing technological skills. These resources enable students to learn at their own pace, revisit complex concepts, and engage visually and aurally, catering to various learning preferences and needs. The literature supports the notion that integrating how-to videos into the learning process can bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application, making them especially valuable for performance-oriented students. However, for mastery-oriented students, these videos also reinforce deep learning by providing detailed, step-by-step instructions that help solidify understanding. This dual utility underscores the role of how-to videos as not just supplementary materials but as central components of effective educational strategies in today's digital learning environments. Given the complexities of

how goal orientation influences learning and the demonstrable benefits of how-to videos in skill acquisition, there was a clear necessity to explore these dynamics through quantitative research, specifically using path analysis. This method can quantitatively dissect the direct and indirect effects of goal orientation on technological skill proficiency, with how-to videos serving as a mediator. Path analysis would allow researchers to understand the strength and significance of these relationships, providing a detailed map of the causal connections and interactions. Such insights are crucial for educators aiming to tailor their instructional approaches to maximize student engagement and skill development. Conducting this type of analysis not only enriches the academic discourse on learning technologies but also guides practical applications in educational settings, ensuring that students' engagement with technology is both effective and aligned with their learning goals.

1.3. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework—This study is grounded in Social Cognitive Theory, as proposed by Bandura (1986). Social Cognitive Theory emphasizes that people learn by observing others, modeling behaviors, and interacting with their environment. Albert Bandura introduced this theory in 1986, highlighting the importance of observational learning and self-efficacy in skill development. This theory is suitable for the study because it explains how students can acquire technological skills by watching how-to videos, which act as models for desired behaviors. It also underscores the role of self-efficacy, where students' belief in their ability to use technology effectively is enhanced through successful observations. Additionally, Social Cognitive Theory supports the idea that goal orientation influences how actively students engage with these videos, thereby mediating the relationship between their goals and the acquisition of technological skills. In support, the Self-Determination Theory, pro-

posed by Deci and Ryan (1985), focuses on the motivation underlying individuals' actions, distinguishing between intrinsic and extrinsic motivations. Edward Deci and Richard Ryan proposed this theory in 1985, emphasizing the importance of autonomy, competence, and relatedness in fostering motivation and psychological well-being. This theory was appropriate for the study as it explores how students' intrinsic motivation (mastery goals) and extrinsic motivation (performance goals) influence their engagement with how-to videos and subsequent technological skill development. Self-Determination Theory helps to understand how goal orientation can affect the degree of engagement and the effectiveness of how-to videos as a learning tool. By fostering intrinsic motivation, students are more likely to engage deeply with the videos, enhancing their technological skills more effectively. This alignment ensures that the study can address both motivational and practical aspects of skill acquisition. Lastly, the study was supported by Multimedia Learning Theory by Mayer (2001). Multimedia Learning Theory posits that people learn more effectively from words and pictures than from words alone. Richard Mayer introduced this theory in 2001, focusing on how the integration of visual and auditory information can enhance understanding and retention of information. This theory is highly relevant to the study as it explains the effectiveness of how-to videos in teaching techno-

The dependent variable of the study was the technological skills of students, or the students' ability to use, manage, and understand technology effectively. The measures of technological skills are proficiency in software tools or the student's ability to use various applications and software effectively; internet navigation and research skills or the student's ability to effectively use the internet to gather information, discern credible sources, and utilize online

logical skills through the combination of visual demonstrations and verbal instructions. Multimedia Learning Theory supports the use of how-to videos as an educational tool that caters to different learning styles, making it easier for students to grasp complex technological concepts. Also, it provides a framework for analyzing how the quality and design of videos can influence learning outcomes, thereby mediating the relationship between goal orientation and technological skill development. By utilizing this theory, the study can better assess how multimedia elements in how-to videos enhance students' technological competencies. Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study, which helps the researcher summarize and briefly state the concept of the study. The independent variable was the goal orientation or the students' underlying attitudes and motivations that direct their approach to learning and achievement. The measures of goal orientation are mastery goal orientation or the student's desire to develop competence and understand new material fully; performance approach orientation or the extent that involves a student's aim to demonstrate superior ability and achieve high grades compared to peers; performance avoidance orientation or the extent when students strive to avoid negative judgments or appearing less competent than their peers; and work-avoidant orientation or the student's aim to complete academic tasks with minimal effort and engagement.

learning platforms; digital communication competence or the process that involves the ability to communicate clearly and effectively using digital platforms, such as email, social media, and collaborative tools; and problem-solving with technology or the ability to use technological resources to find solutions to various challenges. Lastly, the mediator is the how-to videos, which refer to educational resources designed specifically to enhance teaching skills through visual

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study

and interactive content.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—The primary objective of this study was to examine the impact of goal orientation and how-to videos

on the technological skills of Grade 10 students in Sulop District, Davao del Sur, through path analysis. Therefore, the study sought the answer to the following questions:

- (1) What is the extent of goal orientation of Grade 10 students in terms of:
 - (1) mastery goal orientation;
 - (2) performance approach orientation;
 - (3) performance avoidance orientation; and
 - (4) Work-avoidant orientation?
- (2) What is the extent of technological skills of Grade 10 students in terms of:
 - (1) proficiency in software tools;
 - (2) Internet navigation and research skills;
 - (3) digital communication competence; and
 - (4) Problem-solving with technology?
- (3) What is the extent of how-to videos usage?
- (4) Is there a significant relationship among goal orientation, technological skills of students, and the usage of how-to videos?
- (5) How do how-to videos mediate the relationship between goal orientation and technological skills of Grade 10 students?

1.5. Hypotheses—The following hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

H01: There is no significant relationship among goal orientation, technological skills of students, and how-to videos usage. H02: How-to videos do not significantly mediate the relationship between goal orientation and technological skills of Grade 10 students. For a more comprehensive understanding, the following terms were defined operationally: Goal Orientation It is defined conceptually as the underlying attitudes and motivations that direct their approach to learning and achievement. In this study, the independent variable is described in terms of mastery goal orientation, perfor-

mance approach orientation, performance avoidance orientation, and work-avoidant orientation. Technological Skills It was defined conceptually as the ability to use, manage, and understand technology effectively. In this study, the dependent variable is described in terms of proficiency in software tools, internet navigation and research skills, digital communication competence, and problem-solving with technology. How-to Videos It was defined conceptually as the educational resources designed specifically to enhance teaching skills through visual and interactive content. In this study, the mediating variable refers to the factor that was expected to explain the relationship between the independent and dependent variables.

2. Methodology

This section outlines the research design, research participants, research ethics, research instruments, research procedures, data collection, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher employed a quantitative research design, specifically the descriptive-correlational technique through path analysis, to collect data, ideas, facts, and information relevant to the study. According to Fischer et al. (2023), a quantitative research design involves systematically collecting and analyzing numerical data to identify patterns, test hypotheses, and quantify relationships between variables. This method used statistical techniques to derive objective conclusions from the data. A quantitative research design was ideal for examining the impact of how-to videos on the relationship between goal orientation and technological skills of students, as it allowed for precise measurement of these variables. By collecting and analyzing numerical data, researchers could objectively evaluate the strength and nature of the relationships between goal orientation, use of how-to videos, and technological skill proficiency. This approach enabled the identification of specific factors that significantly influenced student outcomes, facilitating targeted educational interventions. As noted by Myers et al. (2013), descriptive research methods focus on describing characteristics of a population or phenomenon without influencing variables during the study. This approach involved detailed observation and reporting of the conditions as they existed. Descriptive methods were suitable for the initial stages of this study, where outlining the current state of students' goal orientations, their usage of how-to videos, and levels of technological skills was essential. By providing a comprehensive description of these aspects, researchers could establish a baseline understanding of the educational context and identify specific trends and patterns. This foundational data was crucial for structuring more complex analyses, such as path analysis, to explore deeper relationships between the variables. As defined by Sullivan (2024), correlational research examines the relationship or association between two or more variables to determine if a statistically significant correlation exists. This approach quantified the degree to which variables were related, providing insights into the nature of their connections without implying causation. Employing a correlational research approach was beneficial for this study as it helped to identify initial associations between goal orientation, how-to video utilization, and technological skills. By establishing the presence and direction of correlations, researchers could hypothesize about the potential pathways and interactions among these variables. This information was critical for setting up subsequent analyses, such as path analysis, to explore how these variables might interact dynamically within a specified model. Moreover, Garson (2013) described path analysis as a specialized form of multiple regression that allowed researchers to assess the direct and indirect relationships among multiple variables within a hypothesized model. This statistical technique helped in understanding the causal connections and the strength of impact between variables. Path analysis was particularly appropriate for this study to explore the mediating effect of how-to videos on the relationship between goal orientation and technological skills. It allowed the researchers to model complex relationships, including direct and indirect effects, providing a clear picture of how goal orientations might influence technological skills directly or through the mediation of how-to videos. This sophisticated analysis could help pinpoint specific intervention points and understand the full scope of how educational tools, such as how-to videos, enhance learning outcomes based on different goal orientations.

2.2. Ethical Considerations—Ethical Considerations: The researcher promptly observed the necessary protocols as outlined in the standard guidelines for conducting the research study, with a particular focus on the study protocol assessments, criteria for managing the popu-

lation, and data collection. The survey questionnaires, along with supporting references, were submitted for further evaluation. After receiving approval from the Ethics Committee, the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study.

Informed Consent and Assent

Ensuring informed consent and assent was a fundamental ethical consideration in this study. The respondents were fully informed about the purpose of the study, which was to explore how goal orientation and the use of how-to videos influenced their technological skills. They also learned about the potential benefits of participating, such as contributing to improved educational strategies and gaining better technological proficiency. Additionally, respondents were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without incurring any negative consequences. This clear communication ensured that students understood what participation involved and could make an informed decision about their involvement. For respondents under the age of 18, obtaining parental consent was essential. Parents or guardians received detailed information about the study, including its objectives, procedures, and any potential risks or benefits. They had the opportunity to ask questions and provide their consent before their child participated in the research. This process respected the legal and ethical requirement to involve parents in decisions affecting minors. By securing parental consent, the researcher ensured that the rights and well-being of young respondents were protected. Moreover, respondents received an assent form that explained the study in language suitable for their age. This form reiterated the key points about the study's purpose, procedures, benefits, and their rights, ensuring that the students themselves understood and agreed to participate. Assent was important because it respected the autonomy and agency of the young respondents, allowing them to express their willingness to participate

in the study. The researcher ensured that the language used was simple and clear, making it easy for Grade 10 learners to comprehend the information provided. This approach fostered a respectful and ethical research environment. Additionally, the process of obtaining informed consent and assent was conducted confidentially to protect the privacy of both the respondents and their families. Information provided in the consent forms was stored securely, and only the researcher had access to it. Respondents and their parents were assured that their participation was voluntary and that declining to participate would not affect their academic standing. By maintaining confidentiality and respecting the respondents' rights, the study upheld the highest ethical standards. This careful handling of consent and assent reinforced trust between the researcher and the respondents.

Privacy and Confidentiality

Adherence to the Data Privacy Act of 2012 was paramount in protecting the privacy and confidentiality of the respondents. The researcher collected only the data essential for the study, avoiding any unnecessary personal information that could compromise respondent anonymity. Personal identifiers such as names, addresses, or specific school affiliations were removed or coded to prevent identification. This careful handling of data ensured that respondents' identities remained confidential throughout the research process. All collected data, whether in digital or physical form, were securely stored. Soft copies of data were password-protected and, if necessary, encrypted to prevent unauthorized access. Hard copies were kept in locked filing cabinets with restricted access. The researcher limited data access to authorized personnel directly involved in the study, all of whom were bound by confidentiality agreements. These measures complied with ethical standards and legal requirements, safeguarding the respondents' information against potential breaches. After the study

concluded and the results were published, the researcher followed standard procedures for data disposal. Hard copies of data were shredded or incinerated to ensure destruction. Soft copies were permanently deleted using secure data-erasure software, rendering the information unrecoverable. This process ensured that all personal data was disposed of responsibly, maintaining confidentiality even after the study's completion and upholding the highest ethical standards in research data management.

Conflict of Interest

To ensure the integrity of the research, it was crucial to acknowledge and manage any potential conflicts of interest. The researcher declared that there were no financial, personal, or professional relationships that could inappropriately influence the study's outcomes or interpretation of data. This study was conducted independently, without any external sponsorship from organizations that might benefit from specific results. Additionally, the researcher disclosed any potential conflicts to the Graduate School Research Ethics Committee and ensured that all findings were reported honestly and transparently.

2.3. Research Respondents—The study involved a sample of 232 Grade 10 students, selected from an estimated total of 550 students in Grade 10 in Sulop District, Davao del Sur. This sample size was determined using the Slovin Formula, a statistical tool commonly utilized in research to ensure a representative sample with a reasonable margin of error. By applying this formula, the study aimed to achieve accurate insights into the technological skills, goal orientations, and usage of how-to videos among Grade 10 students. This methodological approach helped ensure that the results could be generalized to the broader student population in the district. Consequently, involving 232 respondents struck a practical balance between manageability and reliability. The selection of the respondents was carried out using

the Simple Random Sampling Technique. This technique ensured that each student within the target population had an equal chance of being chosen, helping to prevent bias and maintain a fair representation of the group. First, the researcher compiled a master list of Grade 10 students across the public secondary schools in Sulop District. Second, each name was assigned a unique number, which was then randomly drawn using a computer-generated random number list. Lastly, the students corresponding to these randomly selected numbers were identified as the study's official respondents. Several inclusion criteria were established to ensure that the chosen respondents aligned with the study's focus. Only Grade 10 students, ages 15 to 18 years old, who were officially enrolled in public secondary schools in Sulop District were considered. Those who were willing to participate and could provide parental consent (for those under 18) were deemed eligible. Students currently enrolled in special intervention programs or distance education setups that significantly differed from the standard classroom environment were excluded. These criteria helped maintain a clear and relevant respondent profile, ensuring the data collected was directly applicable to the research questions.

2.4. Research Instrument—The researcher made use of an adapted and modified survey questionnaire to suit the current investigation. The first part measured the goal orientation of Grade 10 students. This variable was measured through four domains: mastery goal orientation, performance approach orientation, performance avoidance orientation, and work-avoidant orientation. The Cronbach's alpha value for this instrument is 0.864, which is described as very good and interpreted as reliable. Responses were collected using a 5-point Likert scale to assess the extent of agreement or disagreement with each statement, with subsequent analysis based on predefined ranges of means that effectively categorized the data.

Range of Mean	Description	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The goal orientation of Grade 10 students is always manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The goal orientation of Grade 10 students is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The goal orientation of Grade 10 students is sometimes manifested.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The goal orientation of Grade 10 students is seldom manifested.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The goal orientation of Grade 10 students is never manifested.

The second part of the instrument measured the technological skills of Grade 10 students. This variable consisted of items divided into four domains: proficiency in software tools, internet navigation and research skills, digital communication competence, and problem-solving with technology. The Cronbach’s alpha value for this instrument is 0.932, which is described as excellent and interpreted as highly reliable. The data collection utilized a 5-point Likert scale, allowing respondents to indicate their

level of agreement or disagreement with each statement. This method provided a quantifiable measure of attitudes and perceptions, which was critical for accurately assessing the impact of goal orientation and how-to videos on technological skills. The gathered responses were then analyzed using predefined mean ranges to systematically categorize the data, facilitating a deeper understanding of the underlying trends and patterns within the responses.

Range of Mean	Description	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	The technological skills of Grade 10 students is always evident.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	The technological skills of Grade 10 students is oftentimes evident.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The technological skills of Grade 10 students is sometimes evident.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	The technological skills of Grade 10 students is seldom evident.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	The technological skills of Grade 10 students is never evident.

The third part of the instrument focused on the usage of how-to videos. The Cronbach’s alpha value for this instrument is 0.918, which is described as excellent and interpreted as highly reliable. Responses were gathered using a 5-

point Likert scale, allowing for precise measurement of agreement or disagreement with each item. This data was then analyzed using predefined mean ranges to categorize and interpret the results effectively.

Range of Mean	Description	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very Extensive	How-to videos is always utilized.
3.40 - 4.19	Extensive	How-to videos is oftentimes utilized.
2.60 - 3.39	Moderately Extensive	How-to videos is sometimes utilized.
1.80 - 2.59	Less Extensive	How-to videos is seldom utilized.
1.00 - 1.79	Not Extensive	How-to videos is never utilized.

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure—The researcher took several steps in conducting the study. These are as follows: Permission to Conduct the Study

The initial step in securing permission to conduct the study involved the researcher ob-

taining an endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School. This endorsement served as a formal recognition and support of the research project, validating its academic merit and alignment with the institution’s research objectives. Subsequently, the researcher applied

for ethical clearance from the Graduate School RMC-Research Ethics Committee (GSRMC-REC). The ethical clearance was crucial as it ensured that the study adhered to established ethical standards, particularly in terms of confidentiality, consent, and the overall welfare of the respondents. Once the endorsement and ethical clearance were secured, the researcher approached the Schools Division Superintendent in Davao del Sur to request permission to conduct the study within the schools of Matina District. This request included attaching copies of both the endorsement from the Dean and the ethical clearance certificate to demonstrate compliance with academic and ethical standards. Following approval from the superintendent, the researcher contacted the principals of the individual schools in Sulop District. During this phase, the researcher explained the study's purpose, its potential benefits for the educational community, and the specific roles and expectations of the schools and their teachers, ensuring transparency and fostering cooperation.

Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire

The first step in distributing the questionnaire involved selecting research respondents, who were chosen based on established inclusion criteria, ensuring that all respondents were bona fide Grade 10 students from Sulop District. This was followed by a pilot test conducted on a small group of respondents (not more than 30) to ensure the clarity and reliability of the questionnaire. The pilot test helped identify any ambiguities or biases in the questions, allowing the researcher to make necessary adjustments. This testing phase was crucial for validating the questionnaire's effectiveness in accurately collecting the intended data. Following the successful pilot test, the primary distribution of the research questionnaires occurred. The selected respondents were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaire, ensuring they could provide thoughtful and thorough responses. Re-

spondents had the flexibility to choose their preferred method of completion, either face-to-face or online, accommodating their convenience and comfort levels. This approach not only facilitated a higher response rate but also accommodated the diverse preferences and schedules of the respondents, potentially enhancing the quality and accuracy of the data collected. The final phase involved retrieving the completed questionnaires. The researcher established a deadline for submission, which was communicated clearly at the time of distribution. Respondents submitted their completed questionnaires through the predetermined method, either returning the physical documents in face-to-face settings or submitting them electronically. Once all questionnaires were collected, the researcher proceeded with data analysis, using statistical software to quantify the results and examine the extent of goal orientation, technological skills among students, and the effectiveness of how-to videos.

Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data

The collation and statistical treatment of data in the study, which investigated the impact of goal orientation and how-to videos on the technological skills of Grade 10 students within Sulop District in Davao del Sur, began with the careful organization of retrieved survey data. Upon collection, each questionnaire was carefully reviewed to ensure completeness and accuracy. The data was then entered into Microsoft Excel, a versatile tool for organizing and managing large datasets. In Excel, data were systematically tallied, and entries were categorized based on variables such as goal orientation, students' technological skills, and the use of how-to videos. This preliminary organization was crucial as it set the foundation for accurate and effective analysis, facilitating the identification of patterns and trends within the collected data. Following the initial organization in Excel, the study progressed to descriptive statistical analysis to summarize and describe the features of

the dataset. This phase involved calculating the mean and standard deviation for the scale variables, including goal orientation, technological skills of students, and the effectiveness of how-to videos. The mean provided an average value, offering insights into the central tendency of responses for each variable. These statistics were essential for understanding the general behavior of the data, as they helped highlight common tendencies and the diversity within respondents' answers. Descriptive statistics painted a clear picture of the baseline characteristics of the sample, thereby contextualizing the subsequent inferential analysis. The final stage of data analysis involved applying inferential statistics to explore the relationships and effects among the variables. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation was used to determine the strength and direction of the linear relationships between variables, including goal orientation, students' technological skills, and the use of how-to videos. Additionally, Path Analysis, a form of structural equation modeling, was employed to assess the hypothesized relationships between multiple variables, providing a comprehensive view of direct and indirect influences. This advanced statistical technique enabled the researcher to understand the mediating effect of how-to videos on the relationship between goal orientation and technological skills of Grade 10 students, offering a nuanced insight into the dynamics at play. The use of Pearson correlation and Path Analysis provided robust evidence to support or refute the theoretical constructs proposed in the study, thereby informing targeted educational interventions. After collating and statistically treating the data, the researcher proceeded to interpret and discuss the results. This phase involved synthesizing the statistical findings to ascertain the implications of the mediating effect of how-to videos on the relationship between goal orientation and technological skills of Grade 10 students. The researcher highlighted significant correlations and the impact of predictive

variables on outcome measures. This interpretive process was crucial for understanding the practical significance of the data, allowing the researcher to draw informed conclusions and formulate evidence-based recommendations for enhancing teacher support and professional development initiatives.

2.6. *Data Analysis*—The researcher utilized the following statistical tools in processing the gathered data:

Mean

In this study, this refers to the average score derived from the teachers' responses regarding goal orientation, students' technological skills, and the use of how-to videos. This provides answers on SOPs 1, 2, and 3.

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation

In this study, the linear relationship between variables such as goal orientation, technological skills of students, and the use of how-to videos was assessed. It will provide an answer to SOP 4.

Model Fit Indices

Model fit indices in this research were used to evaluate how well the data fit the hypothesized measurement model in the path analysis. Indices such as the Chi-square, RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation), CFI (Comparative Fit Index), and TLI (Tucker-Lewis Index) were calculated to assess the adequacy of the model structures in representing the relationships among goal orientation, students' technological skills, and how-to videos. This provides a portion of the answer to SOP 5.

Path Analysis

Path analysis through Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) in this context was a multivariate statistical analysis technique that allowed for the examination of complex causal relationships between variables involved in goal orientation, students' technological skills, and the use of how-to videos. It involves estimating direct and indirect effects within the proposed model to understand how variables, such as how-to videos,

mediate the relationship between goal orientations and the technological skills of students. This provides an answer to SOP 5.

Sobel z-Test

In this study, the Sobel z-test was employed to determine the significance of the mediating effect of how-to videos on the relationship be-

tween goal orientation and the technological skills of Grade 10 students, using path analysis. This test calculates the standard error of the indirect effect of the mediator, providing a z-score to assess whether the mediation is statistically significant, thus verifying the strength of the indirect paths within the SEM model.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the study's objectives, as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extents of goal orientation, technological skills among junior high school students within Sulop District in Davao del Sur, and how-to videos usage; the significant relationship among these variables; and the impact of goal orientation and how-to videos on the technological skills of Grade 10 students within Sulop District in Davao del Sur.

3.1. Goal Orientation among Junior High School Students—The goal orientation of students in this study is measured in terms of mastery goal orientation, performance approach orientation, performance avoidance orientation, and work-avoidant orientation. The extents of this variable and its domains are presented in the tables below.

3.1.1. Mastery Goal Orientation—As shown in Table 1, the goal orientation of junior high school students, in terms of mastery goal orientation, acquired a mean score of 3.09, which is described as moderately extensive. This means that the student's desire to

develop competence and understand new material fully is sometimes manifested. This supports the findings of Mose et al. (2022), which indicate that students with a strong mastery orientation exhibit higher levels of learning readiness, indicating their preparedness to engage with new educational challenges. This finding highlights the importance of cultivating mastery goals to foster resilience and a sustained commitment to academic tasks. According to Romero et al. (2024), promoting mastery orientation can create a learning environment that enhances student engagement and overall performance.

Among all statements, Noticing students focusing on improving their skills instead of comparing themselves to others obtained the highest mean score of 3.28, described as moderately extensive. Conversely, the lowest mean of 2.97, indicating a moderately extensive level, was observed in the statement "Experiencing peers who keep practicing even after mastering basic steps." Roen and Måkestad (2019) noted that mastery-oriented feedback in simulation training enhances learners' performance and intrinsic motivation. This suggests that mastery

goals not only drive academic achievement but also prepare individuals for adaptive learning in diverse settings. Hence, integrating mastery-oriented strategies in education can significantly contribute to students' holistic development and adaptability.

3.1.2. Performance Approach Orientation—In Table 2, the goal orientation of junior high school students in terms of performance approach orientation got a mean score of 3.31 with a descriptive rating of moderately extensive. This means that the student's aim to demonstrate

Table 1. Goal Orientation among Junior High School Students in Terms of Mastery Goal Orientation

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Noticing students focusing on improving their skills instead of comparing themselves to others.	3.28	Moderately Extensive
Observing learners asking for extra help to understand challenging topics.	3.11	Moderately Extensive
Seeing classmates trying different methods to solve problems until they succeed.	3.09	Extensive
Recognizing students celebrating personal progress rather than only final results.	3.09	Moderately Extensive
Experiencing peers who keep practicing even after mastering basic steps.	2.97	Moderately Extensive
Realizing that learners stay motivated, even when the task is difficult.	3.02	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.09	Moderately Extensive

superior ability and achieve high grades compared to peers is sometimes manifested. Gómez and Valdés (2019) asserted that students with a moderate level of performance approach orientation tend to excel in environments where external evaluation and recognition are emphasized. This suggests that such an orientation can enhance motivation and outcomes in structured educational settings, provided that supportive teaching practices are implemented. Notably, the statement "Realizing that learners focus on proving their competence in front of everyone" scored the highest, with a mean of 3.52, classified as extensive. Conversely, the statement "Recognizing students competing with

each other for the top score" received the lowest mean score of 3.11, but still falls within the moderately extensive range. Vogt (2022) noted that supportive assessment strategies in performance-oriented classrooms enhance students' focus on achievement and measurable outcomes. This emphasizes the importance of structured support systems that align with students' motivation to perform well in competitive environments. Therefore, fostering an environment that balances guidance and recognition is essential for students with a moderate level of performance approach orientation (Hoque et al., 2020).

3.1.3. Performance Avoidance Orientation—This particular domain of goal orientation of junior high school students acquired a mean score of 3.39, classified as moderately extensive. This indicates that the extent to which students strive to avoid negative judgments or appearing less competent than their peers is sometimes evident among the respondents within the classroom. This supports the view of Usán et al. (2019) that students with moderate performance avoidance orientation tend to exhibit lower academic motivation, which negatively

impacts their academic performance. Meanwhile, the statement Noticing students feeling anxious when they think others might see them fail had the highest mean of 3.70, falling into the extensive category. In contrast, the statement with the lowest mean of 3.22, still rated as moderately extensive, was Realizing that learners worry more about not appearing weak than about improving. As noted by Stasielowicz (2019), performance avoidance goals are negatively correlated with adaptive responses to challenging tasks, thereby limiting students' ability

Table 2. Goal Orientation among Junior High School Students in Terms of Performance Approach Orientation

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Noticing students aiming to score higher than their classmates on tests.	3.38	Moderately Extensive
Observing learners seeking praise and recognition from teachers for good work.	3.36	Moderately Extensive
Seeing classmates take on tasks that showcase their abilities to the class.	3.19	Moderately Extensive
Recognizing students competing with each other for the top score.	3.11	Moderately Extensive
Experiencing peers who feel energized when they surpass others in performance.	3.30	Moderately Extensive
Realizing that learners focus on proving their competence in front of everyone.	3.52	Extensive
Mean	3.31	Moderately Extensive

to achieve academic success. As noted by Choi et al. (2022), fostering mastery-oriented goals may improve students’ resilience and adaptability in academic contexts.

Table 3. Goal Orientation among Junior High School Students in Terms of Performance Avoidance Orientation

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Noticing students feeling anxious when they think others might see them fail.	3.70	Extensive
Observing learners avoiding tasks that seem too challenging or risky.	3.28	Moderately Extensive
Seeing classmates trying to hide their mistakes instead of correcting them.	3.53	Extensive
Recognizing students becoming quiet in group work to avoid negative feedback.	3.35	Moderately Extensive
Experiencing peers who choose easier tasks to prevent looking incompetent.	3.26	Moderately Extensive
Realizing that learners worry more about not appearing weak than about improving.	3.22	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.39	Moderately Extensive

3.1.4. Work-Avoidant Orientation—As shown in Table 4, the goal orientation of junior high school students in terms of work-avoidant orientation yields a mean score of 3.28, categorized as moderately extensive. This means that the attitude of students to complete academic tasks with minimal effort and engagement is sometimes manifested. This finding is consistent with those of Harnar et al. (2021), who suggest that students with a work-avoidant orientation may complete assignments with the least possible effort, primarily motivated to finish tasks quickly rather than learn from them. Such students often lack intrinsic motivation and may experience lower academic achievement as a result. As noted by Stoeger and Zeidner (2019), this orientation can undermine the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills, which are essential for success in more complex educational contexts.

Table 4. Goal Orientation among Junior High School Students in Terms of Work-Avoidant Orientation

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Noticing students avoiding extra assignments or practice to save time and energy.	3.33	Moderately Extensive
Observing learners handing in incomplete work just to meet basic requirements.	3.16	Moderately Extensive
Seeing classmates preferring quick fixes rather than thorough understanding.	3.30	Moderately Extensive
Recognizing students putting minimal effort into group projects.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
Experiencing peers who procrastinate or constantly seek shortcuts in learning.	3.57	Extensive
Realizing that learners choose the easiest tasks to avoid challenging themselves.	3.17	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.28	Moderately Extensive

Among the statements, the highest reported mean of 3.57, falling into the extensive category, was observed for the statement Experiencing peers who procrastinate or constantly seek shortcuts in learning. Conversely, the statement "Recognizing students putting minimal effort into group projects" had the lowest mean of 3.15, although it still falls within the moderately extensive range. Kalali Sani et al. (2021) emphasized the role of goal structures in the classroom, suggesting that emphasizing mastery goals over performance goals can decrease competitive pressures and promote learning for understanding rather than for external rewards. By creating a classroom environment that values effort and learning improvement, educators can help shift students away from work avoidance towards more adaptive and beneficial learning orientations.

3.1.5. Summary on Goal Orientation— The goal orientation of junior high school students in Sulop District, Davao del Sur, got an overall mean score of 3.27, classified as moderately extensive. The result shows that different goal orientations are somewhat prevalent among junior high school students in the Sulop

District, Davao del Sur. Among the domains, the Performance Avoidance Orientation scored the highest mean of 3.39, described as moderately extensive. On the other hand, Mastery Goal Orientation has the lowest mean score of 3.09, although it is still rated as moderately extensive. The moderately extensive rating on goal orientation among junior high school students indicates that the underlying attitudes and motivations that direct their approach to learning and achievement were sometimes manifested. This supports the view of Feyzioğlu (2019) that students with balanced achievement goal orientations demonstrate improved inquiry-based self-efficacy, effectively fostering their ability to approach scientific problems. Furthermore, the results were similar to those of Suyatna and Putra (2020), who found that students with a moderate goal orientation engaged more consistently in reflective thinking and strategic problem-solving. This finding reinforces the idea of Sánchez-Cardona et al. (2021) that goal orientation not only influences students' persistence but also shapes the quality of their cognitive engagement in learning tasks.

Table 5. Summary on Goal Orientation among Junior High School Students in Sulop District, Davao del Sur

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Mastery Goal Orientation	3.09	Moderately Extensive
Performance Approach Orientation	3.31	Moderately Extensive
Performance Avoidance Orientation	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Work-Avoidant Orientation	3.28	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.27	Moderately Extensive

3.2. *Technological Skills among Junior High School Students*—The technological skills of students in this study were measured in terms of proficiency in software tools, internet navigation and research skills, digital communication competence, and problem-solving with technology. The extents of this variable and its domains are presented in the tables below.

3.2.1. *Proficiency in Software Tools*—This particular domain of technological skills among junior high school students acquired a mean score of 3.45, categorized as extensive. This means that. This finding was consistent with Akudo’s (2022) observation that students demonstrated a high level of proficiency in using software tools, particularly for basic tasks in academic settings. While they effectively utilized common applications, their skills with advanced software and emerging technologies were also evident. Lavrentieva et al. (2019)

noted that these collaborative practices, supported by digital tools, prepare students for the kind of team-based work that is common in most modern workplaces. Meanwhile, the highest mean score of 3.65, or extensive, is for the statement Experiencing peers troubleshooting minor issues while using different software tools. Conversely, the lowest mean score of 3.21 was observed for students who noticed creating well-organized documents using word processing software, which falls under the moderately extensive category. Terry et al. (2019) noted that the use of software tools in educational settings fosters the development of organizational skills and strategic thinking as students plan, execute, and review their work using digital platforms. Therefore, proficiency in software tools not only enhances individual learning but also builds essential competencies for effective teamwork and communication in a digitally connected world.

Table 6. Technological Skills among Junior High School Students in Terms of Proficiency in Software Tools

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Noticing students creating well-organized documents using word processing software.	3.21	Moderately Extensive
Observing learners designing presentations with proper formatting and visuals.	3.35	Moderately Extensive
Seeing classmates using spreadsheets to perform basic calculations and organize data.	3.45	Extensive
Recognizing students editing photos or videos using basic editing software.	3.57	Extensive
Experiencing peers troubleshooting minor issues while using different software tools.	3.65	Extensive
Mean	3.45	Extensive

3.2.2. *Internet Navigation and Research Skills*—As shown in Table 7, the technological skills of junior high school students, in terms of internet navigation and research skills, have a mean score of 3.39, indicating a moderate level of proficiency. This means that students’ ability to effectively use the internet to gather information, discern credible sources, and utilize online

learning platforms is sometimes evident in the classroom. The result aligns with the proposition of Zgambo and Chawinga (2019) that, although students with a moderate level of internet navigation and research skills can locate general information online, they struggle with evaluating sources and using advanced search techniques.

Table 7. Technological Skills among Junior High School Students in Terms of Internet Navigation and Research Skills

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Noticing students finding reliable sources for assignments using online search engines.	3.69	Extensive
Observing learners navigating websites efficiently to gather necessary information.	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Seeing classmates evaluating the credibility of online content before using it.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
Recognizing students bookmarking useful web pages for future reference.	3.63	Extensive
Experiencing peers following safe and responsible online practices while browsing.	3.11	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.39	Moderately Extensive

Among the statements on this particular domain, the highest mean score of 3.69 is for Noticing students finding reliable sources for assignments using online search engines, described as extensive. In contrast, the statement Experiencing peers following safe and responsible online practices while browsing which received the lowest mean score of 3.11, was still categorized as moderately extensive. Ay and Erdem (2020) pointed out that internet users, including students, face skill-related problems such as selecting relevant search results and understanding advanced online tools, which limits their overall research efficiency. As noted by Atoy et al. (2020), students’ internet navigation skills remain moderate, requiring further support and training.

3.2.3. *Digital Communication Competence*—In terms of digital communication competence, the technological skills among junior

high school students were described as extensive with a mean score of 3.43. This means that students’ the ability to communicate clearly and effectively using digital platforms, such as email, social media, and collaborative tools is oftentimes evident. According to Zhao et al. (2021), students’ ability to effectively use digital tools for communication was influenced by personal factors such as prior experience and confidence. Consequently, students with strong digital communication skills were better prepared for academic and professional tasks in a technology-driven environment (Rodríguez-García et al., 2022). Moreover, the highest mean score of 3.76 was observed for the statement Recognizing students maintaining proper online etiquette during virtual interactions which falls on extensive category. Conversely, the statement Seeing classmates sharing files and collaborating effectively through digital platforms

received the lowest mean score of 3.02, categorized as moderately extensive. Nazarenko et al. (2023) asserted that introducing digital learning tools significantly improved students' informational and communicative competence. The au-

thor emphasized the importance of integrating digital platforms into education to enhance students' ability to communicate and collaborate effectively.

Table 8. Technological Skills among Junior High School Students in Terms of Digital Communication Competence

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Noticing students composing clear and polite emails to teachers or classmates.	3.50	Extensive
Observing learners participating actively in online discussions or forums.	3.57	Extensive
Seeing classmates sharing files and collaborating effectively through digital platforms.	3.02	Moderately Extensive
Recognizing students maintaining proper online etiquette during virtual interactions.	3.76	Extensive
Experiencing peers using chat tools to ask questions or clarify ideas in group work.	3.32	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.43	Extensive

3.2.4. Problem-Solving with Technology— In terms of problem solving with technology, the technological skills among junior high school students got a mean score of 3.26, rated as moderately extensive rating. This implies that the ability to use technological resources to find solutions to various challenges is sometimes evident. Malik et al. (2019) noted that a moderate level of technological skills in problem-solving among students can significantly impact the teaching and learning processes. As students demonstrate an ability to use technology to solve problems, albeit inconsistently, educators are presented with opportunities to develop these skills further. The highest scores within this domain were observed for the statement Noticing students finding so-

lutions to software errors without immediate help, with a mean of 3.50, categorized as extensive. Conversely, the statement "Recognizing students applying logic to resolve compatibility issues between devices" received the lowest mean score of 3.00, classified as moderately extensive. Unal and Cakir (2021) noted that effectively integrating technology into problem-solving processes not only enhances the ability to address complex problems but also deepens understanding by engaging learners in meaningful tasks. Problem-solving with technology is not solely about technical skills but also involves critical thinking and strategic planning, enabling students to navigate and manipulate digital environments to achieve specific goals (Santos-Trigo Reyes-Martínez, 2019).

3.2.5. Summary on Technological Skills— The technological skills of junior high school students in public secondary schools in Sulop District, Davao del Sur, yielded an overall mean score of 3.38, indicating a moderate level of pro-

ficiency. This means that the students' ability to effectively use, manage, and understand technology is sometimes evident among junior high school students. This supports the view of Abd Karim and Mustapha (2022) that students with

Table 9. Technological Skills among Junior High School Students in Terms of Problem-Solving with Technology

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Noticing students finding solutions to software errors without immediate help.	3.50	Extensive
Observing learners troubleshooting connectivity issues during online activities.	3.16	Moderately Extensive
Seeing classmates using online tutorials to fix technical problems independently.	3.15	Moderately Extensive
Recognizing students applying logic to resolve compatibility issues between devices.	3.00	Moderately Extensive
Experiencing peers experimenting with different tools to achieve the desired outcome.	3.48	Extensive
Mean	3.26	Moderately Extensive

technological skills often prefer learning environments that incorporate digital tools, which can lead to higher motivation and better learning outcomes. This was supported by Koyuncuoglu’s (2022) idea that technology can transform learning from a passive to an active process, as students use tools to construct knowledge rather than merely receive it. The highest scores were observed in Proficiency in Software Tools, marked as extensive, with a mean of 3.45.

Conversely, Problem-Solving with Technology received the lowest mean score of 3.26, though it still falls within the moderately extensive category. The result was consistent with the idea of Chiu et al. (2019) that integrating technology in education can provide personalized learning experiences, allowing students to learn at their own pace and according to their own interests and needs, thereby potentially increasing their engagement and retention of information.

Table 10. Summary on Technological Skills among Junior High School Students in Sulop District, Davao del Sur

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Proficiency in Software Tools	3.45	Extensive
Internet Navigation and Research Skills	3.39	Moderately Extensive
Digital Communication Competence	3.43	Extensive
Problem-Solving with Technology	3.26	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.38	Moderately Extensive

3.3. *How-to Videos Usage among Junior High School Students*—Results in Table 11 show that the usage of How-to Videos among junior high school students acquired a mean score of 3.20, categorized as moderately extensive. This means that educational resources designed specifically to enhance teaching skills through visual and interactive content is sometimes utilized inside the classroom. According to Ugulu

(2019), people learn better from words and pictures than from words alone, making how-to videos an effective educational tool. These videos can cater to diverse learning styles, particularly benefiting those who are visual or auditory learners. The ability of how-to videos to break down complex processes into manageable, repeatable steps makes them highly valuable for reinforcing learning and providing learners with the means to review material at their own pace.

Table 11. Summary on How-to Videos Usage among Junior High School Students in Sulop District, Davao del Sur

Statement	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Noticing students frequently accessing how-to videos to understand new concepts.	3.11	Moderately Extensive
Observing learners following step-by-step instructions from videos to complete tasks.	3.09	Moderately Extensive
Seeing classmates discussing content they learned from how-to videos.	2.97	Moderately Extensive
Recognizing students pausing and replaying parts of videos to grasp difficult steps.	3.28	Moderately Extensive
Experiencing peers recommending specific how-to videos to each other.	3.53	Extensive
Observing students applying techniques demonstrated in how-to videos in practical assignments.	3.26	Moderately Extensive
Noticing learners comparing different how-to videos to find the most effective one for their needs.	3.16	Moderately Extensive
Mean	3.20	Moderately Extensive

Meanwhile, the range of means on this particular variable ranges from 2.97 to 3.53. The highest mean score, 3.53, was on the statement 'Experiencing peers recommending specific how-to videos to each other,' falling under the 'extensive' category. Conversely, the lowest mean score of 2.97 was for seeing classmates discussing content they learned from how-to videos, although it was still rated as moderately extensive. Powell and Bodur (2019) pointed out that the moderate level of usage of how-to videos in educational settings has significant implications for teaching and learning processes. Even with only moderate engagement,

how-to videos can serve as supplementary resources that reinforce traditional teaching methods (Faath-Becker Walker, 2020).

3.4. *Relationship among Goal Orientation, Technological Skills among Junior High School Students, and How-to Videos*—The results of the analysis on the relationship among goal orientation, technological skills among junior high school students, and how-to videos within Sulop District, Davao del Sur, are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis, using the Pearson product-moment correlation, was employed to determine the relationship among the variables mentioned.

Table 12. Relationship among Goal Orientation, Technological Skills, and How-to Videos among Junior High School Students in Sulop District, Davao del Sur

Variables	Technological Skills	How-to Videos
Goal Orientation	0.678**	0.837**
	0.000	0.000
Technological Skills	1	0.443**
		0.000

Note. *Significant at $p < 0.05$. Legend: Perfect Correlation for $r = 1.00$; Strong Correlation for $0.7 \leq r < 1.00$; Moderate Correlation for $0.3 \leq r < 0.7$; Weak Correlation for $0.3 > r > 0.00$; No Correlation for $r = 0.00$.

The findings in Table 12 indicate a moderate correlation between goal orientation and technological skills, with an r -value of 0.678 and a p -value of 0.000, indicating statistical significance. This suggests that students who exhibit higher levels of goal orientation tend to demonstrate moderately stronger technological competencies. This supports the findings of Chonsalasin and Khampirat (2022), who found that students with a mastery goal orientation, who focus on developing competence and understanding rather than demonstrating their abilities, tend to explore technology more thoroughly and persistently. This depth of engagement enables them to develop a robust skill set that supports both academic and personal technological pursuits. Similarly, a strong correlation was observed between goal orientation and how-to video usage, with an r -value of 0.837 and a p -value of 0.000. This indicates that students with a more robust goal orientation are likely to engage with instructional videos more frequently and effectively. In support of this, Zhou et al. (2020) emphasized that self-directed learners with clear goals actively seek out resources, such as how-to videos, to enhance their skills and knowledge. Elareshi et al. (2022) similarly highlighted that digitally engaged students are keen on applying accessible video tutorials to acquire new competencies or clarify misconceptions. This relationship suggests that fostering goal-oriented mindsets could lead to greater utilization of multimedia resources, thereby promoting continuous learning outside traditional classroom structures. Lastly, a moderate correlation was found between how-to video usage and technological skills, with an r -value of 0.443 and a statistically significant p -value of 0.000. This implies that frequent engagement with instructional videos is associated with moderately higher digital competencies. This finding was consistent with those of Chen et al. (2021), who argue that guided visual and auditory inputs can enhance comprehension and skill acquisition,

particularly when learners are motivated to apply what they have learned. In practice, students who frequently view and implement instructions from how-to videos may gain confidence in handling software, troubleshooting technical issues, or experimenting with digital tools. Over time, this iterative exposure to video-based learning can significantly contribute to the development and refinement of technological skills.

3.5. Path Analysis on the Impact of Goal Orientation and How-to Videos on the Technological Skills of Grade 10 Students—The path coefficients in Table 13 reveal several noteworthy insights into how goal orientation (GO) and how-to video usage (HTV) affect students' technological skills (TS). First, the direct path from GO to TS (Estimate = 1.037, $p < .001$) suggests a strong, positive influence, implying that highly goal-oriented students tend to develop more advanced technological skills. Conversely, the path from HTV to TS (Estimate = -0.357, $p < .001$) indicates a negative relationship, suggesting that frequent use of how-to videos might not always translate into improved technological competencies, at least in this sample. Moreover, the path from GO to HTV (Estimate = 0.984, $p < .001$) confirms a significant positive association, indicating that students with higher goal orientation are more likely to engage with how-to videos. In examining the parameter estimates, the indirect effect of $GO \rightarrow HTV \rightarrow TS$ is -0.351 ($p = 0.000$), indicating a significant mediating path but with a negative coefficient. The direct effect of GO on TS (1.037, $p = 0.000$) remains positive and highly significant, while the total effect (0.685, $p = 0.000$) is slightly lower, suggesting partial mediation through HTV. In other words, while a substantial portion of GO's impact on TS is direct, there is also a mediating component through how-to videos that slightly diminishes the net effect. This phenomenon could imply that, despite greater engagement with video resources among goal-oriented students, the type or manner of usage may not

Fig. 2. Path Analysis Model

always foster higher technology skills and may, in certain contexts, even detract from them. Regarding the ratio index of -0.5124 and the Sobel z-test value of -3.0815 ($p = 0.000$), these figures affirm the significance of the indirect (mediating) path and underscore its negative direction. The negative ratio index implies that the mediator (HTV) not only influences the relationship but does so in a counterintuitive manner, re-

ducing the overall effect of goal orientation on technological skills. Such a result may stem from overreliance on step-by-step instruction, which could impede deeper exploration or creative problem-solving skills. Educators could explore strategies to ensure that how-to videos reinforce rather than inhibit the development of robust technological competencies.

Table 13. Path Analysis on the Impact of Goal Orientation and How-to Videos on the Technological Skills of Grade 10 Students

Steps	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p-value
(Step 1) GO → TS	1.037	0.085	12.243	<.001
(Step 2) HTV → TS	-0.357	0.072	-4.958	<.001
(Step 3) GO → HTV	0.984	0.042	23.266	<.001
Step 4 (Parameter Estimates)				
Effect Type	Parameter Estimates	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value / p-value
Indirect Effect Components	GO → HTV → TS	-0.351	0.072	-4.849 / 0.000
Direct Effect	GO → TS	1.037	0.085	12.243 / 0.000
Total Effect	GO → TS	0.685	0.049	14.053 / 0.000

Note. Ratio Index = -0.5124; Sobel z-Test value = -3.0815, $p = 0.000$.

Legend: GO = Goal Orientations; TS = Technological Skills of Students; HTV = How-to Video Usage.

The reported model fit indices indicate an exceptionally good fit, with the Chi-Square at 0.000 signifying no significant difference be-

tween the hypothesized model and the observed data. Moreover, an RMSEA of 0.000 suggests a virtually perfect fit of the model to the data,

which is highly desirable though uncommon in complex models. The CFI and TLI values of 1.000 further reinforce this conclusion, reflecting that the model explains the data with maximum adequacy compared to a baseline model. These ideal indices imply that the hypothesized relationships among goal orientation, how-to video usage, and technological skills align well with observed outcomes in the sample. Consequently, such optimal fit supports the robustness of the structural paths tested, providing confidence in the theoretical underpinnings and practical implications of the model. From a theoretical standpoint, these findings present a nuanced

picture in relation to Bandura’s Social Cognitive Theory and Mayer’s Multimedia Learning Theory. While Bandura’s framework suggests that students with higher self-efficacy and clear goals will proactively seek resources and thus enhance their skills, the negative mediating role of how-to videos indicates that seeking those resources does not always equate to better learning outcomes. Meanwhile, Mayer’s multimedia learning principles are partially supported, as the use of videos can be beneficial, but only if learners interact with the content in ways that promote deep cognitive processing.

Table 14. Model Fit Indices

Index / Metric	Value
Chi-Square	0.000
RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation)	0.000
CFI (Comparative Fit Index)	1.000
TLI (Tucker-Lewis Index)	1.000

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section presents the researcher’s conclusions and recommendations. The discussion is supported by the literature presented in the first chapters, and the conclusion aligns with the statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to evaluate the impact of goal orientation and how-to videos on the technological skills of Grade 10 students through path analysis, utilizing a non-experimental quantitative design with a descriptive-correlation technique. The researcher selected 232 junior high school students from Sulop District, Davao del Sur, as respondents using a simple random sampling method. The researcher utilized modified and enhanced survey questionnaires, which were pilot-tested in a nearby school to ensure the high reliability and internal consistency of the instrument’s items. The results of the study are summarized as follows: First, the goal orientation among junior high school students in Sulop

District was characterized as moderately extensive, suggesting that students sometimes set and pursue academic goals. Among the specific dimensions, performance approach and performance avoidance orientations are more noticeably manifested compared to mastery and work-avoidant orientations, which appear less consistently evident. Second, the technological skills of junior high school students in Sulop District are characterized as moderately extensive, reflecting that these competencies are evident but not consistently so across all domains. Students demonstrate notable strength in using software tools and communicating digitally, with these skills appearing more frequently in their academic tasks. In contrast, their abilities in inter-

net navigation, research, and problem-solving with technology are present to a lesser extent, suggesting specific areas where targeted instruction could further enhance their digital competence. Third, the findings indicate that junior high school students exhibit a moderately extensive usage of how-to videos as a supplementary educational resource. Peer-driven activities, such as recommending specific videos, appear to be the most prominent behavior, highlighting the social aspect of digital learning. However, there is room for more consistent engagement in deeper interactions with the video content, suggesting an opportunity for educators to integrate these tools more systematically to enhance learning outcomes. Fourth, the findings reveal that students with a strong goal orientation tend to exhibit more advanced technological skills and are more inclined to engage with how-to videos. These significant relationships highlight a synergistic interplay among the variables, suggesting that motivational factors substantially influence both digital competence and the utilization of multimedia instructional tools. Additionally, the moderate association between technological skills and the use of how-to videos underscores the role of digital resources in supporting the development of practical skills in educational settings. Lastly, the analysis indicates that students' goal orientation has a strong direct effect on enhancing their technological skills while also significantly predicting their engagement with how-to videos. Although students with higher goal orientation tend to use more how-to videos, this engagement appears to offset the direct positive impact on their technological skills partially. Overall, the model demonstrated an excellent fit, substantiating the robust interrelationships among goal orientation, how-to video usage, and technological competencies among Grade 10 students.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the findings of this study, several conclusions were generated: The study concluded that the goal orien-

tation of junior high school students in Sulop District was moderately extensive, with similar levels observed across mastery, performance approach, performance avoidance, and work-avoidant dimensions. This balanced yet moderate manifestation suggests that, although students intermittently engage in goal-directed behaviors, there is considerable scope to enhance their intrinsic motivation and adaptability in learning. Consequently, targeted educational interventions that promote stronger mastery goals and address avoidance tendencies could lead to improved academic engagement and outcomes, fostering a more resilient and self-regulated learning environment. On one hand, technological skills among junior high school students in Sulop District are moderately extensive, with students demonstrating strong capabilities in software tool proficiency and digital communication competence. However, their internet navigation and problem-solving skills are less consistently evident, indicating specific areas where focused improvement is needed. These findings suggest that targeted instructional strategies that enhance research and problem-solving components within the curriculum could foster a more balanced digital proficiency, thereby better preparing students for the demands of a technology-driven world. On the other hand, the use of how-to videos among junior high school students is moderately extensive, indicating that these digital tools are sometimes integrated into their learning processes. Notably, the prominence of peer recommendations highlights the influence of social learning on students' engagement with video content, suggesting that they are inclined to share and seek guidance through these resources. These findings imply that educators can capitalize on the social dynamics of peer recommendations by incorporating how-to videos more deliberately into the curriculum, thereby enhancing digital literacy and collaborative learning environments. Furthermore, findings suggest that a strong goal orientation

was closely linked to enhanced technological skills and increased engagement with how-to video resources, underscoring the pivotal role of student motivation in digital competency development. Moreover, the observed relationship between technological skills and the use of how-to videos implies that integrating multimedia resources can further support and enrich students' digital learning experiences. These outcomes suggest that educators should consider designing interventions that simultaneously foster goal-oriented mindsets and incorporate effective multimedia tools to advance technological proficiency in junior high school students. Furthermore, the analysis demonstrates that goal orientation exerts a strong direct influence on the technological skills of Grade 10 students, underscoring the importance of clear, self-directed academic goals for enhancing digital competence. Additionally, while engagement with how-to videos is positively related to goal orientation, its mediating role appears to diminish somewhat the direct benefits of goal orientation on technological skills, suggesting that excessive reliance on such resources may not always translate into improved digital performance. These findings suggest that educators should design interventions that foster robust goal-setting practices and encourage a balanced, critical approach to engaging with multimedia instructional materials, thereby optimizing the development of students' technological skills. These partially align with Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory and Mayer's Multimedia Learning Theory in terms of emphasizing learner engagement and resource utilization, but also highlight potential pitfalls when instructional materials do not foster or require more active, generative learning strategies.

4.3. Recommendations—In light of the study's findings, the following recommendations are offered to inform policy, school leadership, teaching practice, and future research:

DepEd Officials. DepEd officials should in-

tegrate the findings into policy development by promoting digital literacy initiatives that foster goal orientation and effective multimedia engagement among students. It is recommended to invest in updating curriculum guidelines to include structured use of how-to videos alongside conventional teaching strategies. Additionally, DepEd should support nationwide professional development programs that equip educators with best practices for leveraging technology to enhance learning outcomes.

School Heads. School heads are advised to cultivate an environment that prioritizes goal setting and sustained academic motivation, ensuring that technology is used as a tool for deeper learning rather than superficial engagement. They should facilitate the adoption of innovative practices, such as incorporating curated how-to video resources into school-wide digital literacy programs. Additionally, school heads can organize regular training sessions and collaborative meetings with teachers to share effective strategies that enhance students' technological skills.

Teachers. Teachers should actively integrate how-to videos and other digital resources into their lesson plans to reinforce and extend students' understanding of complex topics. They are encouraged to foster a classroom culture that promotes goal orientation and self-regulated learning, thereby enhancing students' technological competencies. Moreover, educators should continually assess the effectiveness of digital tools and adjust their instructional approaches to maximize the impact on students' problem-solving and research skills.

Students. Students are advised to set clear and challenging learning goals and to seek out digital resources that actively support their academic growth. They should engage critically with how-to videos by pausing, reflecting, and applying demonstrated techniques in practical assignments rather than relying solely on passive viewing. Additionally, students can ben-

efit from collaborating with peers to discuss and compare digital content, thereby improving their overall technological proficiency and adaptability.

Future Researchers. Future researchers should explore further the mediating factors that influence the relationship among goal orientation, multimedia resource usage, and technological skills, using robust longitudinal and

experimental designs. It is recommended that researchers examine contextual variables across different educational settings to validate and expand upon these findings. Collaboration with educational institutions and policy makers will also be vital to developing evidence-based strategies that enhance digital literacy and student engagement in technology-driven learning environments.

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